

Toxic studies of endocrine disrupting chemicals by machine learning and molecular modeling

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Abstract

High-throughput screening of endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) is of significant to the health risk assessment of various chemicals. We have constructed prediction models using machine learning and graph neural network GCN to identify Persistent, Bioaccumulation, Toxic (PBT) substances or Persistent, Mobile, Toxic (PMT) substances. Among these screened chemicals, we evaluated the endocrine disruption of many chemicals. Based on the prediction model, relevant online prediction server was built and the high-throughput prediction software was also developed. To elucidate the underlying mechanisms of EDCs, we investigated the molecular initiating events (MIEs) using molecular modeling and cell-based assays. The key events after chemical exposure were identified and the adverse outcome pathways (AOP) were proposed.